

The Social Significance of the Development of Ethnic Tourism in Uzbekistan

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Abstract:

This article discusses the issues of the Social significance of the development of Ethnic Tourism in The Republic of Uzbekistan.

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Today, the attention to tourism in our country is developing day by day. In particular, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to ensure the accelerated development of tourism in the Republic of Uzbekistan" is an important basis for this. The decree reads: "Creating favorable economic and organizational conditions for the rapid development of tourism as a strategic sector of the economy, more complete and effective use of the huge tourism potential of the regions, radical improvement of tourism management, creation of national tourism products and their promotion in world markets. Forming a positive image of Uzbekistan in the field of ... " ¹ A number of measures have been developed for this purpose. In paragraph 1 of the decree "Accelerated development of tourism in the country, more complete and effective use of the huge tourism potential, along with traditional cultural and historical tourism, visit other potential types of tourism - ecological, educational, ethnographic, gastronomic, sports, health, rural, industrial, business tourism and the rapid development of other species... " was emphasized. ²

Currently, the interest in ethnic tourism in the world is growing. Along with the development of tourism in the country, it helps to preserve the unique customs and traditions of the regions of the country.

Ethnic tourism is a type of cultural tourism in which a tourist gets acquainted with the life, cultural characteristics and lifestyle of an ethnic group belonging to a particular nation during a visit to the country.

This type of tourism is especially well developed in multi-ethnic and multi-ethnic countries. In particular, Uzbekistan is known around the world as a country with huge ethno-cultural and cultural-historical potential. There are many unique and invaluable reserves of ethnic resources for the development of ethnic tourism. Because more than 130 different nationalities live in Uzbekistan. Each of these nations has its own way of life, customs, culture and language.

Tourism, as a leading sector of the world economy, plays a significant role in the socio-economic development of countries. Undoubtedly, one of the fastest growing sectors of the world economy is tourism. Today, tourism accounts for 9.8% of world GDP, 7% of exports of goods and services, 30% of total services and 9.5% of total employment. Every eleventh new job in the world is created within the tourism industry. Uzbekistan is a country with significant potential for tourism development. This is also due to the presence of many unique natural objects (lakes, mountain peaks), rich cultural and historical heritage. The number of foreigners visiting the Republic of Uzbekistan is growing every year. For the last 15 years, the number of visits of foreign citizens to Uzbekistan has increased 15.5 times, or from 442.1 thousand in 2002 to 2847.9 thousand in 2017. Visits of citizens of Uzbekistan abroad in 2017 amounted to 5182.5 thousand people, which is 6.5 times more than in 2002.

The distribution of visitors to the Republic of Uzbekistan based on tourist destinations (2017) is as follows:

^{1, 2} Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to ensure the accelerated development of tourism in the Republic of Uzbekistan." December 2, 2016, No. PF-4861.

2017 yilda O'zbekiston Respublikasiga kelgan chet el fuqarolari sonining safar maqsadlari bo'yicha taqsimlanishi, ming kishi

Table 1.1. Distribution of tourists visiting Uzbekistan by purpose

As can be seen from this table, the largest segment of tourists falls on tourism for the purpose of visiting relatives. This in turn includes ethnic tourism.

Ethnic tourism is a type of tourism that serves to strengthen interethnic tolerance through deep learning of the people's own culture and the culture of other peoples.

Ethnic tourism is one of the types of tourism that is attractive to many countries as a form of cultural and educational tourism. World practice shows that tourism is able to meet the various spiritual needs of people through such a direction. The most important aspect of ethnic tourism is to get acquainted with the traditions and culture of these different ethnic groups. Customs and traditions are the principle of relations between the people of the country, they mean the rhythm and rhythm of life, values and moral principles. The characteristic of customs is an indicator that reflects the analysis of certain traditions, their place and role in the life of the people, as well as their peculiarities.

The role of traditions is not the same in all aspects of social life. While this has a small impact on the country's economy, it has a high impact on the people's beliefs and religion. Accordingly, if certain customs and traditions are adopted at the same time by a certain group of members of the community, another part may reject them. For this reason, customs are divided into positive (traditionally accepted) and negative (traditionally rejected) types.

Thus, ethnic tourism allows tourists to see traditional residential and farm buildings, meet locals dressed in national costumes, participate in traditional festivals and ceremonies, taste traditional dishes of the national cuisine, and purchase souvenirs reminiscent of ethnic lifestyles. After returning to their home country, the tourist shares his impressions with friends and family members and introduces them to the information he received during the trip. All this in itself serves to increase tolerance between nations and peoples.

At the present time, in the context of rapid development of scientific technology, ecological crisis, increasing information flow, the problem of "survival" of nations is a problem. The most promising way to preserve ethnic diversity in the regions is through ethnic tourism.

Ethnic tourism is one of the types of exotic tourism in which a tourist gets acquainted with the life, cultural characteristics and lifestyle of an ethnic group belonging to a particular nation during a visit to the country. This provides an opportunity for scholars as well as interested individuals to explore the roots of their own nation or other peoples. Even through the use of this type of tourism, many people have been able to find their distant relatives from different parts of the world. Sometimes people want to go to places where they spent their youth or to areas where their ancestors lived. For this reason, the second name of this type of tourism is also called nostalgia tourism.³ It is this feeling of longing that makes people want to learn a certain culture rather than relax on the waves.

There are many migrants in the world and they can be divided into two types:

- Mandatory
- Optional

There have been many reasons for forced migration in history, including military, social, or religious reasons. It is safe to say that the reason for voluntary migration is the desire of people to live a better life. This is why people have migrated to other countries or to distant continents.

Any type of tourism is the result of interethnic relations, all of which encompass certain elements of ethnotourism.

At the same time, the interest in the ethnic culture of different peoples around the world is growing day by day. In particular, we can see that ethnic thinking is growing in our country. Particular attention is paid to the preservation of ethnic and cultural heritage, the interaction between tourism and culture, taking into account the specificity and diversity of culture, as well as the solution of problems.

Today, the interest in ethnic tourism in the world is growing day by day. This, along with the development of tourism in the country, will help to preserve the unique customs and traditions of the regions of the country. This type of tourism is especially well developed in multi-ethnic and multi-ethnic countries. There are many foreign literatures on ethnic tourism, which give different definitions of this type of tourism.

³ Petroman I., Petroman K., Buzatu K., Marin D., Dumitrescu A., Statie K., Rus I. A Religious and Ethnik Tourism Profile of Europe // Skientifik Papers Animal Skienke and Biotechnologies. - 2011. - №44(2). - P.490-493.

Ethnic tourism is:	Source:
It is a type of travel that aims to fully or partially get acquainted with the early (primitive) culture.	Define Ethnotourism // Travel Industry Dictionary.
The main difference of cultural tourism from other types of tourism is that the main focus is not on nature, but on people and reveals the lifestyle of the local population.	Bolnikk S. Promoting the culture sector through job creation and small enterprise development in SADK countries: the ethno-tourism industry. - ILO, 2003.
As part of cultural tourism, it is to get acquainted with the culture and language of individual peoples.	Sunduchev Ch.B. Ethnic tourism as one of the areas of cultural and educational tourism / №2009. - S.53-56
Tourism that aims to acquaint the tourist with the cultural or ethnic heritage of other people who are different from their own ethnic lifestyle and culture.	Harron S., Veiler B., Hall K.M. Ethnic tourism // Special interest tourism. - 1992. - P.83-94.
It is a visit to the place where one is born or raised in one's homeland or relatives.	A.V. Babkin Special types of tourism / A.V. Babkin. - Rostov-on-Don: Phoenix, 2008. -- 252 p.
A type of tourism, the main purpose of which is to get acquainted with "exotic" peoples. ("Exotic" here refers to people who live far away from the tourist destination (remote areas).	Petroman I., Petroman K., Buzatu K., Marin D., Dumitresku A., Statie K., Rus I. A Religious and Ethnic Tourism Profile of Europe // Skientifik Papers Animal Science and Biotechnologies. - 2011. - №44(2). - P.490-493.

Table 1.2. Classification of definitions of ethnic tourism

Analyzing this table, it can be concluded that to date, a clear rule of ethnic tourism has not yet been developed by scientists. Often ethnotourism is understood as a definite manifestation of it.

There are many views on the concepts of ethnic and ethnographic tourism, the similarities and differences between them. For example, the Russian researcher A.I. Shukin distinguishes between these two concepts in his research and says, "If the main participants in ethnographic tourism are a group of people engaged in ethnography, ethnic tourism covers a wide audience, ie users of this type of tourism are individuals with spiritual goals. ." puts forward the idea that.

In the views of M.A. Julina, ethnic and ethnographic tourism are considered synonymous concepts. V. Smith substantiates the concept of ethnic tourism as a different type of cultural and historical tourism.

In recent years, in addition to the concept of ethnic tourism, concepts such as jayloo, anthropological tourism and aboriginal tourism have also been used.

In foreign and Russian literature, ethnic tourism is also called cultural tourism ("sultural heritage tourism", "heritage tourism", "diaspora tourism"). This concept is defined by the US National Fund for the Protection of Historical Monuments: "Cultural tourism is a reflection of human history. is to visit places of interest. "

The International Council for the Preservation of Historical Monuments and Attractions (ICOMOS) defines cultural tourism differently: "Cultural tourism is a special type of tourism (among other purposes) that promotes the discovery of new monuments and attractions. "

The closest concept to ethnic tourism is the concept of ethno-cultural tourism. It in turn includes ethnographic anthropology, sand tourism, and so on.

In our opinion, sandstone (genealogical), ethnographic, aboriginal tourism, anthropological and djailoo tourism can be conditionally listed as components, ie directions of ethnic tourism. This is because the tour program that is sometimes implemented can depend on several ethnic tourism types at the same time and link them together.

Classification of ethnic tourism. Below we describe in detail the types of ethnic tourism:

Figure 1.1. Classification of ethnic tourism

The direction of sand tourism (nostalgic tourism, genealogy tourism, ancestral tourism) is a specific type of tourism - a visit to the place where a person was born or where his ancestors lived. The emergence of sand tourism is a process associated with the return of generations of migrants and ex-prisoners by the British Tourism Authority (BTA) and the study of their ancestors, a type of tourism that has been evolving since 1999.

Today, this type of tourism is especially popular in Central European countries, where migration became widespread during World War II, for example, the visits of Bugafins to Karelia, Leningrad, the Germans to Kaliningrad and the Japanese to Sakhalin.

Genealogical tourism is one of the fastest growing tourism sectors, according to a study by the University of Illinois. It is especially developed in Scotland, where more than 1 million tourists visit every year to find their relatives. According to experts, as a result of further development of this type of tourism in the Scottish tourism industry, revenue is expected to reach 2.4 billion US dollars.

A clear example of sand tourism is the group of Finnish citizens around Lake Ladoga. During the 1939-1945 war, more than 500,000 Finns were forced to flee their homeland. After being allowed to move to the Leningrad region, they moved to Leningrad en masse, and ethnic tourism took on a mass character.

It is possible to create a sufficiently diverse and unique tourist programs on sand tourism. In most cases, an individual tourist route is created for each tourist. Because every tourist visits the places where he or his relatives live, and during the visit he starts to look for the places and graves of their ancestors. In doing so, it conducts inquiries from the indigenous population of the area. But unfortunately, in recent years, sand tourism has been slowly declining. This is due to the fact that the younger generation is less interested in their ancestors and their history.

Ethnographic orientation is a type of tourism that aims to obtain information and entertain, which introduces a large number of tourists to the life, clothing, language, folklore, traditions, customs and culture of a particular nation. This type of tourism preserves the ancient appearance of elements of folk culture in everyday life, traditional forms of land use, its own historical and architectural image, the village.

involves getting to know the people and their art.

In this case, the villages (settlements) are divided into types: real and demonstrative population (living in another point and going to work elsewhere).

Anthropological tourism is a form of ethnographic tourism that aims to compare the culture and past lifestyles of extinct ethnic tribes with modern lifestyles by familiarizing themselves with the lifestyles of a small number of endangered peoples. makes A vivid example of this is a visit to Peru to study the culture of the lost Incas or to get acquainted with the culture of the Scythians in danger of extinction in the Crimea. Another declining nation is the Indians of the Embera tribe, and the number of visitors to Panama to get acquainted with the ethnic life of this people is increasing day by day.

Aboriginal tourism (aboriginal tourism, indigenous tourism) is a type of tourism that directly attracts the local population to the tourism industry. In doing so, the natives travel around the area where they live in order to learn more about the culture of their people. This may include several day excursions.

An example of this is the Akha Hill tribe in northern Thailand. Members of this tribe show visitors a true Thai lifestyle. There will be wonderful trips through tea plantations and rice fields, as well as visits to valley-shaped bungalows, forests and waterfalls, where every Thai will have the opportunity to feel like a true representative of the nation.

Djailoo - it is one of the youngest types of ethnic tourism. The term is derived from the Kyrgyz language and means "Djailoo" - "Alpine lawn", "mountain pasture". Djailoo tourism is a type of tourism that allows you to live a little longer during this primitive system, far removed from this civilization. Djailoo tourism emerged in Kyrgyzstan in the late 1990s, when local tour operators allowed tourists to live in mountain shepherds' homes for a while and get acquainted with their way of life. This type of travel was first tested by tourists from Switzerland, Germany, the UK and Russia. To date, Kyrgyzstan is the leading country in terms of tourism. One of the most popular tourist routes is the tours organized along the shores of Lake Issyk-Kul. For example: "Bishkek - Korchorka village - Sarala - Saz - Bishkek" tourist route. During this route, tourists will get acquainted with the nomadic folk culture, national games, alakiizi and shirda fabrics, as well as felt rugs and have the opportunity to ride horses.

Ethnic tourism is a separate type of tourism, which is not well covered in the literature to date, such as agrotourism, ecotourism, sports tourism. Therefore, there is insufficient information on its classification and classification of the main geographical features.

An important feature of ethnic tourism is the diversification of its composition, taking into account the needs and interests of tourists.

In ethnic tourism, the preparatory stage is important in the development of a tourist route. One of the main conditions for the development of this type of tourism in the planned area is the collection of all necessary documents, plans and materials. Then it is necessary to study the current socio-economic situation in the region.

Forming a database of investment proposals and assessing the level of opportunities to expand investment; it is necessary to establish contacts with organizations interested and willing to develop ethnic tourism. In addition, a comprehensive marketing study is required to study the potential of ethnic tourism in the region, the level of conditions for the development of this tourism, the state of tourism thinking among the population and the level of desire and efforts to form this type of tourism in their region.

An effective model for the development of ethnic tourism in Uzbekistan has not yet been developed. The main condition for the development of this type of tourism is to attract the population of areas with these ethnic resources to engage in this type of tourism and the formation of infrastructure in rural areas. Another distinctive feature of this tourism is that it allows the income to be used to improve the tourism infrastructure and lifestyle of the population.

An important task of ethnic tourism development projects is the sustainable development of ethnic tourism in short-term trends through the active involvement of indigenous peoples. The fact that a small number of locals have taken their own independent management in the implementation of ethnic tourism projects guarantees that this type of tourism will soon achieve sustainable and efficient development.

In our view, ethnic tourism covers three components:

- Indigenous peoples living a traditional way of life;

- Cultural landscape as a result of economic activity of the people;
- Traditions and ceremonies (holidays) that are an integral part of the local culture;

The general rules for the successful development of ethnic tourism and the preservation of traditional culture and traditional cultural landscape are as follows:

- Conservation of the nature of the area should be considered as a basic condition for the preservation of the cultural landscape;
- Consideration of the local population as full-fledged partners in expanding the flow of tourists to the region;
- Interaction between locals and tourists should be orderly. In this case, it is necessary to follow the formula "Guest-host", "Equally".

The realization of ethnic tourism will require a long-term state program aimed at its comprehensive development at a time when tourism is considered as a source of additional income, not the main one. The level of prosperity (wealth) of the region should not remain directly dependent on the flow of tourists. When developing such programs, the following should be considered:

- ✓ First and foremost, to ensure the traditional use of nature;
- ✓ Sale of domestically produced products (such as agricultural and handicraft products) at a price that takes into account the added value of traditional methods;
- ✓ Distribution of additional income from traditional farms according to the labor expended by each member of society;
- ✓ Spending the main income from ethnic tourism on regional development (construction and maintenance of roads, construction of new buildings and structures, further development of education and health, financing of housing loans to people with disabilities, large families and young people);
- ✓ Proper and equal distribution of income from ethnic tourism. This excludes competition among locals for income from tourists;
- ✓ Attracting tourists to finance social projects implemented in the region;

Uzbekistan is known all over the world as a country with huge ethno-cultural and cultural-historical potential. There are many unique ethnic resource reserves for the development of ethnic tourism. Because more than 130 different nationalities and ethnic groups live in Uzbekistan. Each of these nations has its own way of life, customs, culture and language.

The socio-economic and political environment of Uzbekistan, in particular, the fact that it has been a colony for almost 150 years, has had a significant impact on its demographic development, including the ethnic composition of the population. The indigenous people of Uzbekistan are Uzbeks. In recent years, the share of Uzbeks in the national population has increased and now stands at 80.0% of the population (8.6% compared to 1989).

Figure 2. Ethnic composition of the population of Uzbekistan

The second indigenous nation of the country is the Karakalpaks. Their total number is 549.2 thousand people or 2.2% of the country's population. Among the indigenous peoples of Central Asia in the Republic of Uzbekistan are Tajiks (1237.4 thousand or 4.9%), Kazakhs (977.8 thousand 3.6%), Kyrgyz (227.4 thousand 0.9%), Turkmens (152.3 thousand 0.6%). The number of Tatars living in Uzbekistan is also significant (275.4 thousand people 1.0%). Along with Russians (1050 thousand 3.8%), Ukrainians, Belarusians, as well as Poles, Czechs, Bulgarians, Koreans, Armenians, Jews, Iranians and other nationalities live in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The geographical location of the nations in the country is also not uniform. The first reason for this is the historical development of nations, and the second is the peculiarities of the development of economic sectors in the republic. Karakalpaks are a nation living entirely within their own republic (94.5%).

Many traditions of the peoples living in Uzbekistan have been intertwined because they have lived in the same area for many years. That is why we can find many similarities in them. In particular, the lifestyles and customs of the fraternal peoples are very close to each other. In our opinion, the majority of tourists visiting Uzbekistan for ethnic tourism come to get acquainted with the cultural life of the Uzbek people. But there are also tourists who want to get acquainted with the way of life of other peoples in Uzbekistan. There are cultural centers of many nationalities in the regions of our country, through which you can get acquainted with the necessary information.

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